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Understanding *Fratelli Tutti* by Understanding ‘Understanding’

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Abstract: Understanding is oft misunderstood as a species of knowledge in philosophy by equating it with propositional understanding. However, understanding – which was regarded as a greater cognitive achievement than knowledge even in ancient Greek philosophy – is desired more than knowledge in both science and philosophy. So, revisiting understanding is the need of the hour by understanding its components, characteristics, and value. This paper aims to give an overall understanding of the notion of ‘understanding.’ Furthermore, by understanding ‘understanding,’ this paper also explores the possibilities of understanding the recent encyclical of the Pope, *Fratelli Tutti*.

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Introduction

We are living in an era, where human dignity and human rights can be evaded by selfishness and self-centred activities. The powerful remain in power and are ready to do anything to retain their power. However, the downtrodden are edged out of the mainstream to the periphery. In this self-centred world, the social encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) by Pope Francis comes as a prophetic call for a better, just, and peaceful world; inviting us to be peacemakers and “men and women prepared to work boldly and creatively to initiate processes of healing and renewed encounter” (FT 225). This social encyclical is an invitation to *understand* ‘the other’ – not only our neighbours but also ‘the strangers on the road’ (FT 56) through the goggles of love and compassion. It is a call “to build bridges, to break down walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (FT 276), by building ‘social friendship’ (FT 233) for ‘a more fair and fraternal future’ (FT 248).

When we read this social encyclical, the first thought that may overpower us could be, “What the Pope says is absolutely right. I have been brought up in a good catholic tradition, and I *know* very well all that Pope Francis tells through his social encyclical.” Of course, I bet that everyone of us know that we are called to be peacemakers (Mt 5:9); to love our neighbours as ourselves (Lev 19:18, Mk 12:31); to love the stranger (Lk 10:25-37) and even to love our enemies (Mt 5:44). Pope Francis also *knows* that his folk *knows* about what he has written. However, what he intends is not to enrich our *spectrum of knowledge* on these teachings of the Church, but in *expanding the horizons of our understanding* on them. The paradox of our times is that we, *knowing* the facts, refuse to *understand* them, and as a result, stay idle to

respond to the need of the hour. Jesus himself said the same about two millennia ago, “you will indeed listen, but never understand, and you will indeed look, but never perceive” (Mt 13:14).

When we say that we *know* but do not *understand*, then we are encountered with a set of spontaneous epistemological questions. “Doesn’t knowledge make me understand? Can’t I understand better when I know more? Is understanding different from knowledge?” Answering these questions will lead us to the ‘the mystery questions’ (Marcel 1949) that the encyclical poses to every individual.

In this paper, I, first, try to clarify the notion of understanding by differentiating it from knowledge. By comparing understanding with knowledge, I claim that understanding is a cognitive achievement and distinctively valuable. To defend my claim, I put forth two arguments: value argument and grasping component argument, which would prove us that understanding is different from knowledge and not a species of the latter. Secondly, I discuss a few unique characteristics of understanding, such as understanding is graded; holistic; requires certain special cognitive abilities other than knowledge abilities, and cannot be transmitted unlike knowledge, rather facilitated to others. Finally, I apply the derived conclusions in understanding *Fratelli Tutti* in the present context.

1. What is Understanding?

The question, “what can we understand?” gives us a variety of answers. We understand a subject matter, a phenomenon, a system, a mathematical calculation or theory, persons, feeling, places, maps, etc. For example, understanding the encyclical “Fratelli Tutti” is different from understanding why my friend got upset with me; or understanding how a computer algorithm functions is different from understanding the causes of recent floods in central Europe, the US and India, or understanding why something is the case is different from understanding how something is the case. Thus, understanding is multifaceted unlike

knowledge, because “knowledge is concerned with propositions, whereas understanding usually isn’t” (Prichard 2010: 74). Since understanding is multifaceted, it can be classified into different categories like propositional, interrogative, factual, objectual, explanatory and symbolic, not to exhaust the list. However, the type of understanding that I am concerned with in this paper is a subject matter, a topic (Elgin 2007, Jäger 2016), or a theoretical framework (Zagzebski 2009).¹

2. Understanding and Knowledge

Since knowledge and understanding are two main cognitive achievements, there is a tendency of titling understanding under knowledge as its species. One of the main reasons could be that one seems to require knowledge of certain body of information regarding a subject matter to understand it (Kvanvig 2003: 191). There is also a tendency to label it as an extension of knowledge, i.e., the more a person knows regarding a subject matter, the better she seems to understand it. Lipton (2004) is one of the proponents of this camp. He writes that “understanding is not some sort of super-knowledge, but simply more knowledge: knowledge of causes” (Lipton 2004: 30). Along with Lipton (2004), certain philosophers of science (like Achinstein 1983, Kitcher 2002, Salmon 1989, and Woodward 2003) also hold that whether it is knowledge-that; knowledge-why, or knowledge-how, when a person gains more of it, then she would understand better. They claim that “understanding why X is the case is equivalent to knowing why X is the case, where this is in turn equivalent to knowing that X is the case because of Y” (Prichard 2010: 74). The philosophers of science seem to zero down any type of understanding to propositional

¹ Understanding a theoretical subject matter, or domain of things is called ‘objectual understanding’ (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 5).

understanding and conclude that understanding is a species of knowledge.

Certain similarities between understanding and knowledge seem to give us the impression that understanding could be a species of knowledge. One of the main similarities is that “both knowledge and understanding involve true belief” (Khalifa 2011: 95). When additional explanations can make a person understand it well, then it seems that assenting to more true beliefs can make a person understand a subject matter. Assenting to true beliefs is nothing but coming to know them. For example, when a person reads a book on climate change by a well-known climate scientist, then she acquires knowledge regarding climate change. The process of knowledge acquisition takes place when she assents to the true beliefs of the climate scientist. So, the more she reads, the better she understands. Thus, assenting to the true beliefs seems to make a person not only know those true beliefs but also understand them.

Another similarity is in terms of conditions of knowledge. Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun (2017) claim that we could get certain conditions of understanding that could parallel the JTB conditions of knowledge. Understanding may require the belief condition, parallel to knowledge, when the understander “has to possess a representation of what is understood. It is further plausible that the representation must in some way be accepted by the agent, and so we get a condition that parallels the belief condition for knowledge” (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Understanding may require the truth condition, parallel to knowledge. “Since understanding is a cognitive success, the representation needs to reflect the relevant facts adequately” (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Thirdly, “it seems that understanding would not be a cognitive success of the agent if the agent could not provide good reasons for the representation that underlies her understanding or if her understanding did not result from a reliable process. This motivates a condition that parallels the justification condition for knowledge” (Baumberger,

Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Thus, understanding seems to require the knowledge conditions, which once again affirm that understanding is not different from knowledge.

Apart from the philosophers of science, certain epistemologists also claim that understanding is a species of knowledge. Both Grimm (2006), who argues from the perspective of the psychological aspect of understanding, and Khalifa (2011), who takes up the antirealist perspective, argue that understanding is a species of knowledge.

However, other epistemologists (Elgin 2007; 2009, Kvanvig 2003, Pritchard 2010, Riggs 2009, and Zagzebski 2001) disagree with these philosophers. One of the main arguments that they employ to distinguish understanding from knowledge is value argument. These epistemologists strongly argue that understanding is distinctively valuable. All cognitive achievements are finally valuable. Understanding is a fundamental epistemic good and a cognitive achievement. Therefore, understanding is finally valuable (Pritchard 2010: 83, 84). When understanding is distinctively valuable, then it cannot be a species of something like knowledge. So, understanding is not a species of knowledge. When Pritchard (2010) and Zagzebski (2001) claim that both knowledge and understanding are distinctively valuable, Kvanvig (2003) makes it only for understanding. For him, only understanding that is distinctively valuable and not knowledge, because for him understanding is distinct from knowing (188).

Setting aside the debate between these two camps of philosophers, when we analyse understanding ourselves, we can observe that understanding seems to require something *more* than knowledge. For mere knowledge of something does not seem to guarantee corresponding understanding. The gained knowledge regarding a subject matter remains only as a chunk of true beliefs, until an extra cognitive work

is done with them. A person needs to do some extra cognitive work other than knowing something in order to understand it. Now the question is, what is this ‘extra element’ that makes a person understand a subject matter, when she knows it already. In order to answer this question, we shall begin with the components of understanding.

3. Components of Understanding

What are the components of understanding? Both epistemologists and philosophers of science would agree that *informational component*² is one of the building blocks of understanding (Boyd 2017: 109). Understanding requires two types of information: (i) *background information*, relevant to the subject matter and (ii) *new information* regarding the subject matter. Relevant background information is a prerequisite for the process of understanding a new body of information. Pritchard (2010) cites a case where certain background familiarity or information becomes a prerequisite to understanding a new proposition. He writes,

Suppose that I understand why my house burned down, know why it burned down, and also know that it burned down because of faulty wiring. Imagine further that my young son asks me why his house burned down, and I tell him. He has no conception of how faulty wiring might cause a fire, so we could hardly imagine that merely knowing this much suffices to afford him understanding of why his house burned down (Pritchard 2010: 81).

Relevant background information regarding faulty wiring helped Pritchard to understand why the house burned down. On the other hand, his son lacks such understanding because he does not know

² The term ‘informational component,’ means a body of *relevant* information regarding a subject matter, which is true and justified. Understanding requires *a body of information*, unlike knowledge, which can be acquired even with a single proposition.

how faulty wiring might cause a fire. Even though he knows that the house burned down due to faulty wiring, he may fail to understand it when he does not have relevant background information.

However, Boyd (2017) claims that *easy understanding* does not require any specialized background information (105). According to him, not all types of understanding need certain specialized background information, except *difficult understanding*. He argues that “most people [in general] possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills..., for which they did not have to conscientiously develop” (Boyd 2017: 120). He claims that most of our understanding falls under *easy understanding*. However, *difficult understanding*, which can be gained only by the experts and epistemic authorities, requires certain specialized background familiarity relevant to the subject matter.

Though Boyd’s claim seems to be very lucrative, it does not rule out the basic and necessary relevant background information that a person requires to understand a new body of information. It is important here to note that *easy understanding* rules out only the sophisticated and esoteric background information, but not the necessary and relevant background information that a person requires even for simple (easy) understanding.

Secondly, an understander needs *new information or a body of new information*, which she aims to understand. In general, new information can be gained through perception, inference, or testimony, whereas memory plays the role of an information reservoir, from which an understander could collect her background information. Normally background information plays a supportive role in understanding new information. However, there are also cases, where new information could play the supportive role in order to

understand already stored information in memory. Say, a person simply assents to a body of new information (X_1) of a speaker at a point of time, t_1 but without understanding it. For unknown reasons she does not pay attention to X_1 at t_1 . While trying to understand another new body of information X_2 at a later point of time, t_2 , she happens to recall the non-understood information X_1 . Now also say, she comes to understand X_1 , with the help of her knowledge regarding X_2 . In this case, the new body of information X_2 at t_2 plays the role of background (supportive) information to understand X_1 , which was stored in memory at t_1 . So, supportive information need not always be background information rather new information as well.

Along with background information, background reasons also support understanding a new body of information. Unlike knowledge, which can be gained even with unrelated body of information, understanding requires both the body of information and reasons to hang together. For example, to understand recent phenomena on climate change, a person requires knowledge regarding gradual hike in the temperature;³ natural catastrophes like floods, forest fire, ice melting in polar glaciers, and the experts' prediction on the future global environmental crisis on the earth etc. She also requires the reasons behind these phenomena, such as CO₂ emission and Greenhouse effect, which caused by the anthropogenic activities etc. Thus, that the cognitive ability connects the links among the pieces of new information and reasons with their relevant background information and reasons, helps a person *grasp* a subject matter (Boyd 2017), which leads us to the second component of understanding.

³ The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Special Report on the Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C (2018) warns, "Human-induced warming reached approximately 1°C (likely between 0.8°C and 1.2°C) above pre-industrial levels in 2017, increasing at 0.2°C (likely between 0.1°C and 0.3°C) per decade" (IPCC 2018: 31)

The second main component of understanding is *grasping*. Unlike the informational component, which is common to both knowledge and understanding, the grasping component is unique to only understanding, because understanding has to do with the way in which a person combines pieces of information into a unified body (Kvanvig 2003: 197), and see how the body of information hang together in an order (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 12; Riggs 2003a: 218).

What is grasping? Grasping can be understood as (a) *fitting or placing the information in its relevant place in the web of information* (Boyd 2017, Elgin 2007; 2017, Grimm 2006, Jäger 2016, Kelp 2015, Lipton 2004, Malfatti 2019a&b, Zagzebski 2009) and (b) *fitting or placing reasons in their relevant places in the web of reasons* (Jäger 2016).

(a) As seen earlier, understanding required both background and new body of information, which need to hang together. However, placing them in the web of information requires understanding their dependency relations. Primarily, an understander requires to gain the grasping relations of parts to other parts and those of parts to a whole (Zagzebski 2009: 144), then “the grasping of explanatory and other coherence-making relationships in a large and comprehensive body of information” (Kvanvig 2003: 192), because “understanding is fundamentally the grasp of dependency relations” (Grimm 2005, Jäger 2016, Zagzebski 2009).

(b) Fitting or placing the reasons along with the information in their relevant places in the web of reasons is to be done parallelly while understanding a subject matter. Jäger (2016) claims that understanding needs the relevant background reasons along with background information. In his ‘Weight-of-Reasons Principle of Understanding,’ he writes that “the degree to which S understands a subject matter is proportional to S’s awareness of the relative epistemic

weight of the total available reasons relevant to propositions belonging to that subject matter” (Jäger 2016: 180). So, the more dependency reasons an understander has regarding a subject matter, the better she understands it.

The grasping component, which is unique to only understanding disproves the claim that understanding is a species of knowledge or an extension of knowledge.

4. Special Characteristics of Understanding

Apart from the value argument and grasping component argument, there are other special characteristics of understanding which would clearly distinguish understanding from knowledge. Philosophers like Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun (2017), Boyd (2017), Elgin (2017), Grimm (2011), Hills (2009; 2016), Jäger (2016), Kvanvig (2003), Malfatti (2019a&b), Pritchard (2010), Wilkenfeld (2013), Zagzebski (2009) list out several special characteristics of understanding. I discuss only four of them not to exhaust the list.

- (i) Understanding is graded
- (ii) Understanding requires certain special cognitive abilities
- (iii) Understanding can be facilitated via testimony
- (iv) Understanding is holistic

5. Understanding is Graded

Unlike knowledge, understanding comes in degrees. Since knowledge is propositional, it is always binary, i.e., either you know it or do not know it. However, understanding is graded (Grimm 2014, Jäger 2016, Moravcsik 1979) and progressive. An epistemic authority’s understanding will be more sophisticated than that of a novice or a layperson in the same domain. When a climate scientist explains the notion of climate change to her students, she would have a more sophisticated sort of understanding regarding climate change than that of her students, even though the latter know what climate change is. In this case,

both the scientist and the students have understanding but in different degrees. The example of Grimm may help us understand that understanding is graded.

When I start chopping onions and my eyes begin to water, I think I understand why my eyes are beginning to water, namely, because I am chopping the onions. I don't think it is because of the time of day, or the colour of the shirt I am wearing, or anything like that; it's because of the onions. But obviously someone with a greater understanding of onion (and eyeball) chemistry would be able not just to identify the onions as the cause but would be able to say what it was about the onions that was bringing this about - in this case, the particular sulphur compounds that were being broken down and released into the air when I did the chopping. What such a person would therefore grasp, which I would not, is that if I were to chop some other vegetable with these same compounds, my eyes would likewise begin to water (*ceteris paribus*); or perhaps, that if I were to chop an onion specially designed to lack these compounds, my eyes would not water; and so on (Grimm 2014: 337).

Grimm writes further, “what these facts seem to illustrate is not that the person who appeals to the compounds understands while I fail to understand, but that understanding comes in degrees; I have less of it, and he has more” (Grimm 2014: 337), the more a person grasps a body of information, the better she understands it.

That understanding comes in degrees implies that understanding is not binary rather progressive. The degree of a person's understanding depends upon not only the available body of information and reasons, but also her cognitive abilities, and the way she uses her cognitive abilities to grasp

the body of information and reasons. I would compare the process of gaining understanding to a spiral. When a person broadens her minimal understanding to higher degrees, she does it with the help of already existing (minimal) understanding. Of course, spiral understanding does not rule out any kind of new understanding at all, rather implies that existing understanding helps a person maximize her understanding to higher degrees.

6. Understanding Requires Certain Special Cognitive Abilities

Understanding requires certain cognitive abilities, without which an understander does not seem to grasp a body of new information (Boyd 2017, Malfatti 2019b, Zagzebski 2009). Though there can be a long list of such cognitive abilities, I list out the main one which are helpful to my current discussion.

The first and basic one is the ability to acquire knowledge of new information. Such cognitive abilities require reasoning and analytical abilities to justify the true beliefs. However, these abilities are common to both knowledge and understanding. The second one is the ability to find out the dependency relations between the different clusters of information and reasons. The third cognitive ability is to place information and reasons in an order and coherently according to their dependency relations in the web of information and reasons. The fourth ability is to gain the whole picture of the already placed information and reasons. The last three cognitive abilities are unique to understanding. There are also other cognitive abilities of understanding such as, gathering relevant body of information and reasons together; comparing and contrasting the gathered information and reasons with one another; finding the missing links among them; fixing them in the web of information and reasons in an order, and finding out a person's doxastic incoherencies and inconsistencies.

Along with these four abilities, there are two more characteristics of an understander. They are: answering new questions regarding the subject matter; the ability to apply explanations to

counterfactual cases and helping a person to understand by explaining a subject matter. These characteristics would function as a litmus test for an understander and help others to know the degree of understanding that an understander possesses regarding a subject matter. For example, when a climate scientist is able to describe a problem regarding the recent floods in different parts of the world clearly; explains it well and answers to the questions posed in a conference of other climate scientists, then it shows that she has a superior and sophisticated understanding regarding climate change, i.e., she owns certain abilities, which help her convert even the esoteric information and reasons into exoteric ones, and thus, make even a novice or a layperson in the domain understand them.⁴

7. Understanding can be Facilitated via Testimony

Testimony plays a vital role in acquiring knowledge and understanding. when knowledge can be transmitted via testimony, the recent debate in epistemology is, whether understanding can also be transmitted via testimony. The pertaining question is whether acquiring understanding

⁴ There are other cognitive abilities for understanding as well. For Wilkenfeld (2013), the cognitive abilities are those which would “manipulate some mental correlate of the understood object such that, in the absence of interfering factors, one would then be able to manipulate the target itself” (1003). For de Regt and Dieks (2005), they are the abilities that would “recognize qualitatively characteristic consequences of [theory] T without performing exact calculations” (151). For Newman (2014) they are problem-solving abilities. He writes “If someone has problem-solving abilities as well, she is properly said to understand a theory, which she can use to comprehend a whole range of phenomena” (59–62). I do not discuss these cognitive abilities because they may not fit in my discussion in this paper.

through ‘understanding-providing testimonial explanations’⁵ (Malfatti 2019a: 478) by a speaker can be called as transmission of understanding. In most cases, explanations seem to provide understanding, the latter being the goal of the former (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 3).

The philosophers of science narrow down the propositions of understanding-why and understanding-how to understanding-what (propositional understanding) and thus, claim that all type of understanding can be called understanding-providing testimonial explanations. The understanding-providing explanations in a testimony seem to help a hearer connect the missing links and grasp the subject matter. For them, that a hearer’s understanding becomes broader with additional explanations in a testimony, proves that understanding can be transmitted.

However, I would say a straightforward ‘No’ to their claim, because the understanding-providing explanations of a speaker can only facilitate understanding in a hearer and cannot transmit understanding of the speaker. Primarily, understanding is the job of the hearer (Zagzebski 2009), and not of the speaker. Understanding depends on the cognitive work of the hearer. The understanding-providing explanations of a speaker merely transmits only the informational component and thus, triggers certain abilities in the hearer to do certain cognitive work to understand the subject matter. So, what a speaker can transmit via testimony is only the informational component of understanding and not the grasping component. However, the speaker can

⁵ Explanations can be of many kinds such as explanation-what, explanation-why and explanation-how. All types of explanations need not always be propositional. They can be tacit, visual; gestural, or symbolic. So, understanding can be gained through non-verbal communication as well, see Lipton (2009) and Khalifa (2013a). However, to make my discussion fit to my current debate, I take all three kinds of explanations as verbal (propositional) explanations.

trigger certain abilities to grasp the new body of information via testimony.

A Speaker can *facilitate* understanding in a hearer by helping him develop his cognitive abilities. An epistemic authority with her methodological superiority can help a novice or a layperson to understand the subject matter through her explanations, or by breaking down the esoteric propositions into exoteric ones. Thus, she helps him develop the necessary cognitive abilities to understand the new body of information. She may also use different methods to help the novice understand the subject matter, such as explanation, cross-examination, or asking ‘why and how’ questions, etc.

When a hearer tries to develop his cognitive abilities on his own, then it takes time for him to do so. However, an epistemic authority, with her methodological superiority and expertise in her domain, can quicken the process of developing cognitive abilities in a hearer by making him realize the inconsistencies in his doxastic attitudes, and reasoning; by showing him how to place his doxastic attitudes and reasons in their relevant places; and by helping him showing the missing link among them. Thus, a hearer can acquire understanding of even esoteric subject matter through the help of an epistemic authority with methodological superiority.

However, Boyd (2017) seems to claim that *easy understanding* can be acquired through testimony, because it “does not require much cognitive effort, nor does it require the possession of any unique or well-developed cognitive skills or abilities or any specialized background beliefs or knowledge” (116). Since the cognitive abilities of *easy understanding* are *not* highly sophisticated as those of *difficult understanding*, he claims that a person will be able to grasp even connections between relevant bits of knowledge in *easy understanding* (Boyd 2017: 115). And so,

he claims that *easy understanding* via testimony could be transmitted because “the grasping that is required for understanding can occur automatically at the level of processing the testified information” (Boyd 2017: 119).

Boyd (2017) seems to parallel the cognitive abilities of *easy understanding* with those of knowledge, by naïvely claiming that *easy understanding* does not seem to require any sophisticated cognitive abilities. He writes that

easy understanding involves understanding for which most people possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills, but for which they did not have to conscientiously develop, and... once these background conditions are in place, one can potentially gain *easy understanding* through testimony since the grasping that is required for understanding can occur automatically at the level of processing the testified information (Boyd 2017: 120).

His claim that the job of the hearer in every knowledge transmission via testimony is “to *make sense of the content* of speaker’s testimony, and to *conceive* of the testifier or the content of her testimony in the *right way*” (Boyd 2017: 117 paraphrased and italicized by author) seems naïve, because he seems to take the grasping component of understanding for granted, by equating it with mere knowledge acquisition. When “people possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills,” (Boyd 2017: 120) of course, grasping can be done without any other *extra* cognitive work. However, this does not mean that understanding can be transmitted by testimony. The already possessed “relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills” still remain as cognitive success of the hearer and not the speaker. Thus, understanding can be gained only as the result of the individual understander’s cognitive work (Zagzebski 2009). And so, it is non-transmittable via testimony.

8. Understanding is Holistic

One of the main characteristics of understanding is that it is holistic in nature (Brogaard 2015, Baumberger, Beisbart and Brun 2017, Elgin 2007; Pritchard 2010). A person can gain knowledge even through a single or a chunk of unrelated propositions. However, understanding requires a body of information, which are not only pieced together by the understander (Kvanvig 2003: 192; Malfatti 2019a&b), but also placed coherently in a relevant order. A person cannot understand a subject matter with a chunk of unrelated information, because along with a body of information, “understanding requires the grasping of explanatory and other coherence-making relationships in a large and comprehensive body of information” (Kvanvig 2003: 192). So, one cannot understand an atomistic information without understanding a larger body of information where it fits in (Brogaard 2005, Pritchard 2010). Therefore, unlike knowledge, understanding is holistic.

We have already seen that understanding requires not only new information and reasons but also background information and reasons. Moreover, understanding is possible only when we thread background information and reasons with new ones and place them in their relevant places in the web of information and reasons. When we fail to grasp any of the informational; explanatory or coherence-making relationships in the web of information, then we would end up in not understanding the subject matter. Though it may be possible for us to understand a few different clusters of information here and there regarding the subject matter, it may not be possible for me to gain an overall understanding of the subject matter, merely because understanding is holistic.

9. Is Understanding Desired Better than Knowledge?

The four special characteristics of understanding contrast understanding from knowledge, and thus, prove that understanding is neither a species of knowledge nor an extension of it. For Kvanvig (2003) understanding is desired better than knowledge. However, desiring understanding better than knowledge is not new to philosophy, “the concept of understanding was central in ancient Greek philosophy” (Moravcsik 1979: 56), because “mere knowledge of truths is of no interest to Plato” but only understanding (Moravcsik 1979: 60). In most of his Socratic Dialogues, Plato seems to aim at helping his interlocuters become aware of their doxastic inconsistencies in their arguments. Moravcsik (1979) further writes that “understanding, according to Plato, involves insight, and this insight is the grasp of, or having an adequate concept of, special abstract entities, the Forms, which make up the domain that understanding is concerned with” (59-60). So, from ancient Greek philosophy it was understanding, which was desired better than knowledge.

When understanding is desired better than mere knowledge, then understanding *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) would be better than having mere knowledge of it. By reading this social encyclical, we may come to know what the Pope wants to tell us through this encyclical. However, mere knowledge should not be our aim, rather understanding *Fratelli Tutti* by understanding what the Pope really invites us to do.

10. Understanding *Fratelli Tutti*

Walking on the footsteps of St. Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis aims, in his *Fratelli Tutti*, to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship (FT 5). It is a call not only to the Catholics, but also to the entire human race to conscientize oneself regarding his/her own very purpose of life on earth.

As I have said in the introduction, the first response of every reader would be to take *Fratelli Tutti* for granted, by saying “Yes, I know it already, because *Fratelli Tutti* reiterates the core Biblical teaching of loving the other.” However, the hidden danger is that when we limit ourselves with mere knowledge acquisition, then we may fall prey to certain epistemic arrogance of knowing things without understanding them. However, understanding *Fratelli Tutti* would open our minds and lead us to action.

In order to understand *Fratelli Tutti*, which is a body of new information, we may have to have a good backup of the background information regarding the major concerns that the Pope has cited in this social encyclical. Firstly, regarding the ‘dark clouds that have covered our world’ such as manipulation of freedom, democracy, and justice; selfishness and indifferent to common good; hunger for modern gadgets; the culture of waste, and disrespect to human dignity etc. Then, we must also get to know the background reasons why we ignore ‘the stranger on the road.’ Secondly, we need to grasp *Fratelli Tutti* in the right way. Grasping *Fratelli Tutti* demands us to place ourselves in the place of victims first. For we must understand that all that the Pope has said need not be a distant happening to a third person elsewhere in the world, and as if they might not affect me and my family here and now. However, grasping *Fratelli Tutti* demands the realization of the bitter truth that “I may be the next victim anytime in the future.” Pope’s concerns raise certain mystery questions, which involve every one of us. When I place myself in the context and use my cognitive abilities to grasp *Fratelli Tutti*, only then my understanding will be holistic.

Most importantly, understanding *Fratelli Tutti* calls for action, which must begin from oneself. One must treat the strangers with respect and dignity, making this world a place for all to live without fear, and teach the future generation to

be so, not only by words but deeds. For being “men and women prepared to work boldly and creatively to initiate processes of healing and renewed encounter” (FT 225) is a collective, synergical and challenging teamwork. Only when we join our hands together, for both prayer and action, then we can fulfil the dream and desire of the Pope and would contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person (FT 8).

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